

HISTORICAL AND MODERN RELATIONS OF UZBEKISTAN WITH THE COUNTRIES OF CENTRAL ASIA.

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Annation: This article talks about the historical and modern relations of Uzbekistan with the countries of Central Asia. Mutual cooperation relations started during the time of the first President of Uzbekistan I. A. Karimov and the current President Sh. M. Mirziyoyev is developing in the top pictures. The article gives brief information about mutual cooperation and contacts being implemented in a friendly manner.

Key words: Uzbekistan, cooperation, Central Asian countries, Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, historical past, sovereignty, independence, brotherhood, economic area.

One of the main directions of Uzbekistan's foreign policy was focused on strengthening cooperation and friendship with the young independent countries of Central Asia - Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, and Turkmenistan. A serious policy based on the unity of the history, culture, language, and roots of these five countries was the path of economic and social development. It should be noted that the President of Uzbekistan I.A. Karimov has been establishing equal and mutually beneficial cooperation between the countries and peoples of this region for the next five years, and has been implementing measures to strengthen and develop it.

The ancient Turanian peoples of Central Asia, who were connected to each other for thousands of years, were divided into different nationalities during the former USSR. Soviet republics were established that were sovereign on paper and dependent on the Center. Due to this false policy, peoples with the same traditions, lifestyles, spiritual and spiritual values were divided into Uzbeks, Kazakhs, Tajiks, Kyrgyz, and Turkmens. formed. They have their own language and culture.

Now to completely unite them is equivalent to finding national values. Moreover, it is natural that the independent states that emerged after the disintegration of the former USSR on the land of Turkestan felt a vital need to get closer to each other in terms of their historical origins, the rich past of the peoples, and their spiritual and spiritual needs. joined together, their spiritual, religious and moral relations were harmonized, their ways of living and customs were common, and they became a single, huge and living entity. As a result, the traditions of unity of blood and brotherhood have been formed.

In the conditions of independence, the perception of the nation, inter-ethnic relations, national culture, cultural heritage of closely related peoples, ethnic problems, geographical and economic unity will change. The socio-political processes emerging in the new historical conditions made it necessary to look at the origin of the peoples of the Central Asian countries, their history, their unique lifestyles and close neighborly relations in a different way than ever before. After all, the countries that are ethnically close to each other,

historically living in the same environment and the culture of the past was born on the same land, but at the same time living as an independent country, are looking for their historical roots, re-establishing the relations of mutual cooperation. considers restoration to be a necessity of life itself. In January 1993, on the initiative of President Islam Karimov, the Tashkent meeting of the leaders of the Central Asian countries was organized.

The Central Asian Commonwealth was founded at this high-level meeting. The leaders of five countries - Kyrgyzstan, Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, and Turkmenistan - signed an agreement on commonwealth. This was welcomed and supported by the people of the region. Thus, a new term "Central Asia" appeared in the world political vocabulary. Of course, politicians, lawyers, and economists of different categories have given different assessments of this event. Some of them even went so far as to say that the countries of the region will unite and become a single country. Who will be the head of the region? Questions such as which language will be the state language, how the problems of the national cultures of the multi-ethnic region will be solved. President Islam Karimov, as the initiator of the establishment of the Central Commonwealth, clearly indicated its purpose and essence. That is, the sovereignty of independent states is included. not to interfere in the system, management method and internal affairs of each other, to respect and recognize the Constitution of each country, to establish only economic and cultural cooperation, to expand the opportunities for the single market, exchange of goods, to eliminate artificial barriers at customs and borders measures were considered. Soon after that, the practical foundation of this commonwealth was laid. In January 1995, the President of Kazakhstan Nursultan Nazarbayev came to Tashkent. A number of documents on economic cooperation between Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan were signed. Kyrgyzstan soon joined this agreement. As a result, it was possible to create a single market and exchange products between the three countries.

The Commonwealth of Central Asia is not only a product of today's transition period, but also a geographical, historical-ethnic and socio-economic necessity. For example, these countries are geographically close to each other and densely located. Water, electricity and other natural factors also connect them. 50 million people have historically a single past, a single destiny, worldviews and traditions that have been harmonized with each other. They have ancient values that are higher than any political and economic commonwealth. There is also a spiritual, cultural, ethical, religious and linguistic commonality that has been formed over thousands of years. Countries and peoples, regardless of their national interests and needs, are looking for ways of mutual cooperation in finding solutions to worldly problems and issues affecting the fate of humanity. cooperation, lifestyles, traditions, and spirituality cannot be compared to the friendship of neighboring nations. Because here the sacred feeling of the connection between the spirit of the ancestors and future generations, the integrity of the whole earth-Motherland is always stable. President Karimov knows that this is the humanitarian content of the policy of strengthening the unity of the peoples of Asia and deepening the relations between the countries of the region.

Currently, the countries located in the Central Asian region have their own natural production opportunities. Almost 20% of the coal, 18% of the gas, 33% of the gold, 26% of the vegetable oil, and 92% of the cotton mined in the period of the former SSR are accounted for by this region. From this issue itself, it became clear how effective it is to establish mutual cooperation between countries that are rich, have developed agriculture, and have innumerable mineral resources. There are not a few people who do. These are, firstly, the

sense of false nationalism formed in the recent past of seventy years, the concept of a part of morality and a certain limitation of the worldview, the lack of a full and deep understanding of regional cooperation, and secondly, the rapprochement of our countries. is the presence of the forces that are in danger. Karimov, who realized the achievements and shortcomings of this road, the existing conflicts, takes a realistic view of the issue and evaluates it objectively.

In July 1993, deepening of economic integration between Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan in 1994-2000 an agreement on measures was signed¹¹⁵. In January 1994, an agreement on the establishment of a single economic zone was signed. The Kyrgyz Republic joined this agreement in April 1994. An Executive Committee coordinating the cooperation between the three countries was formed, and the Central Asian Cooperation and Development Bank was established. As a result of the work of these bodies, the decision of the Council of Prime Ministers of the Republics was signed in Bishkek. In it, the directions of bringing the republics closer to each other economically by the year 2000 were determined.

On July 8, 1994, the state delegation headed by Islam Karimov went to Almaty to participate in the meeting of the heads of state and government of the Republics of Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, and Kyrgyzstan. A one-on-one meeting of the leaders of the three countries was held at the residence of the President of Kazakhstan. Then the negotiations with the expanded structure of the delegations began. At the end of the negotiations, Presidents Islam Karimov, Nursulot Nazarbayev and Askar Akayev jointly adopted a statement and an Address to the people of Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan. Also, the memorandum on cooperation in the field of population migration and the establishment of the Central Asian Cooperation and Development Bank between the three countries, intergovernmental agreements and contracts in the field of social and economic development, as well as in the field of information provision signed agreements.

Economic reforms in the CIS countries, strengthening and development of their cooperation will not be harmed in vain. Instead of making efforts in the field of economic unification, doing practical work in the field of establishing interstate structures that coordinate mutual relations within the CIS, the regional isolation and isolation of some countries is increasing. They are trying to get out of the crisis independently, even if it harms the economic interests of the neighboring countries. Hard-won agreements are often broken by unilateral actions. In particular, the agreement on the establishment of an interstate bank, approved by several parliaments, is being inappropriately canceled, and as a result, this agreement is not being implemented. The agreement on joint security, the agreed rules of financial and credit policy are not being implemented.

All of these are disrupting the field of collective action in various fields of the CIS countries, causing direct economic damage to them, and on top of that, they are causing people's disappointment, creating distrust in the authorities, and dangerously increasing social tension.

We are concerned about the development of events in this way, and we suggest that you hold a meeting of the heads of the Commonwealth of Nations without delay to discuss the following issues

1. About how the consideration of establishing the economic union and its coordinating organizations is being implemented;

2. About the immediate implementation of the agreement on interstate banking, first of all, interstate multilateral settlements based on the creation of the payment union of the CIS;

3. Implementation of the agreement on joint security and the strategic implementation of the CIS on the execution of agreements on the forces.

Over the past years, the head of Uzbekistan visited all Central Asian countries on state visits and created a unique atmosphere in the region. Therefore, on the initiative of our country, on August 11, 2017 in Tashkent, at the international conference on the topic "Central Asia - the main priority of Uzbekistan's foreign policy", Uzbekistan and its neighboring countries will discuss the most important issues of regional importance. Various aspects of modern regional policy, views and approaches of neighboring countries were discussed in detail. This large-scale international conference was organized by the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, International Relations Information and Analysis Center, of the UN Development Program in our country office and projects of the Organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe (OSCE). was organized in cooperation with the coordinator's office. It should be noted that it is this conference. Later, it was the reason for a large international conference to be held in Samarkand.

On the initiative of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, On November 10-11, 2017 "Central Asia: ancient history and common future, sustainable" held in Samarkand international conference on "cooperation for development and progress" and 2018 On March 15 of Astana, the first meeting of the leaders of the Central Asian countries took place meeting was held. These meetings continued in the following years. It can be said that it was the basis for the development of the regional cooperation of the countries.

The next important step in the cooperation of the Central Asian countries is on March 15, 2018 of the leaders of the Central Asian countries, which took place in Astana, the capital of Kazakhstan. It can be said that it was the first consultation meeting. President Sh. Mirziyoyev. Such a meeting was introduced in Samarkand at the suggestion of N. Nazarboyev, It was held in Kazakhstan. It is worth noting that Central Asia will solve the following main tasks at this meeting were proposed by our country as priority areas of cooperation:

First, it is effective in the field of ensuring security and stability in Central Asia search for new reserve and practical mechanisms to expand regional cooperation;

Secondly, trade-economic, innovation, investment, transport-communication, banking-specific programs for partnership in finance, water-energy and cultural-humanitarian spheres development of "road maps";

Thirdly, a broad exchange of views on the most pressing international and regional issues, to agree on a common position on them and then the UN, CIS, SCO and others promotion within international organizations.

CONCLUSION

In short, the Central Asian countries have mutual regional cooperation and they followed their own way of implementing integration. This uniqueness comes from independence and subordination of the Central Asian countries without fully following the path of coordination. It is manifested in the transition to the state. Ultimately, it depends on several factors mutual integration processes have stopped. Today he is the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev's initiatives in foreign policy, especially Uzbekistan Central Asian countries as a result of his policy as a priority direction a new stage

of cooperation has begun. This stage is devoid of any subordination, only includes processes based on mutual cooperation and coordination. That's it is more important to hold large-scale conferences that stimulate each other have .For example, on the initiative of our country, on August 11, 2017, it was held in Tashkent "Central Asia is the main priority of Uzbekistan's foreign policy". international conference "Central Asia: common history and common future, cooperation for sustainable development and progress" and this, in turn, on March 15, 2018 Astana is the first consultative meeting of the leaders of the Central Asian countries caused the organization. At the next stage, such meetings are held every year reliable regional cooperation by establishing and solving problems in the region causing it to become stronger.

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